

Potential Antitubercular Drugs : II. Synthesis of Some Mono-N-Arylamides of Alkylsuccinic Acids[†]

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The preparation and characterisation of some mono-N-arylamides of *n*-hexyl, *n*-decyl, *n*-dodecyl and *n*-hexadecyl succinic acids are described. The antitubercular activity of these acids are also reported.

THE observation by Barry¹ that rocelli acid(I), isolated from the Lichen *lecanora sordida* possesses tuberculostatic properties *in vitro* prompted him and his co-workers^{2,3} to synthesise a number of alkyl substituted succinic acids and their derivatives with a view to study their antitubercular activity. The results were encouraging and the compounds were found to possess, as anticipated, antitubercular activity in various degrees. These authors could also make a rough correlation of antitubercular activity with the number of carbon atoms in the alkyl chain. Somewhat similar studies were carried out later by Joshi and co-workers⁴ with alkylaryl succinic acids.

In view of activity exhibited by such succinic acids and their derivatives it was considered worthwhile to undertake the synthesis of some mono-N-arylamides(VII) of a few alkyl succinic acids(V, *a-d*) and to study their antitubercular activity.

n-Hexylsuccinic acid (V, *d*) was prepared according to Higginbotham and Lapworth⁵. The other succinic acids were prepared by the method due to Bischoff⁶ (Bentley, Perkin & Thorpe⁷). The starting materials were lauric, myristic and stearic acids (II, *a-c*) which were brominated at the α -position by Hell-Volhard-Zelinsky method. The bromo acids were not isolated, rather the intermediate acid bromides were esterified *in situ* when the corresponding esters(III, *a-c*) were obtained. The ethyl esters of the tricarboxylic acids(IV, *a-c*) were then readily obtained from the foregoing crude bromoesters by reaction with diethyl sodiomalonate. Hydrolysis to the tri-acids followed by thermal decarboxylation gave the succinic acids(V, *a-c*). Incidentally, it is interesting to note that all the three tricarboxylic acids have the same decomposition temperature as that (m.p.) of malonic acid. The overall yield of the succinic acids(V) was fairly good in each case.

The desired mono-N-arylamides were prepared from these acids *via* their anhydrides(VI, *a-d*) which were readily obtained by heating the corresponding acid(V) with excess of acetyl chloride. The anhydrides when heated with one molecular proportion of the appropriate primary aromatic amine in benzene solution readily gave the corresponding mono-N-arylamides(VII). The acids(V) and

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TABLE-1 ALKYL SUCCINIC ACIDS(V) AND THEIR ANHYDRIDES(VI)

(A) The Acids	R-CH-COOH CH ₂ -COOH		M. P. and crystalline nature	Mol. formula	Analysis		Required
	% Yield				Found		
1. <i>n</i> -Hexylsuccinic acid	65		87° glistening plates from methanol	C ₁₀ H ₁₈ O ₄	C 59.65 H 9.01	C 59.00	H 8.91
2. <i>n</i> -Decylsuccinic acid	60		94-95 plates from acetic acid	C ₁₄ H ₂₆ O ₄	C 65.19 H 10.12	C 65.11	H 10.07
3. <i>n</i> -Dodecylsuccinic acid	80		101° colourless plates from AcOH	C ₁₆ H ₃₀ O ₄	C 67.23 H 10.15	C 67.15	H 10.41
4. <i>n</i> -Hexadecylsuccinic acid	75		106° colourless plates	C ₂₀ H ₃₈ O ₄	C 70.47 H 11.51	C 71.15	H 11.11
(B) The Anhydrides	R-CH-CO CH ₂ -CO						
5. <i>n</i> -Hexylsuccinic anhydride	55		57° liquid, solidified on cooling	C ₁₀ H ₁₈ O ₃	C 65.45 H 8.93	C 65.21	H 8.70
6. <i>n</i> -Decylsuccinic anhydride	55		68-69° plates pet. ether	C ₁₄ H ₂₆ O ₃	C 70.15 H 10.31	C 70%	H 10%
7. <i>n</i> -Dodecylsuccinic anhydride	60		75° colourless from petroleum ether	C ₁₆ H ₃₀ O ₃	C 71.98 H 10.81	C 71.64	H 10.45
8. <i>n</i> -Hexadecylsuccinic anhydride	59		78° colourless from petroleum ether	C ₂₀ H ₃₈ O ₃	C 74.12 H 11.65	C 74.08	H 11.11

TABLE-2

Sl. no.	Name of the compound	R-CH-COOH CH ₂ -CONH		m.p.°	Molecular Formula	Analysis			Minimum inhibitory concentration mg/ml
		% Yield				Found	Required		
1.	Monoanilide of <i>n</i> -hexylsuccinic acid	57	114	C ₁₆ H ₂₃ NO ₂	C 69.45 H 8.52 N 5.43 eq. wt. 272.5	C 69.31 H 8.3 N 5.05 eq. wt. 277.00		100.00	
2.	Mono <i>p</i> -chloroanilide of <i>n</i> -hexylsuccinic acid	32	123	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ ClNO ₂	C 62.00 H 7.27 N 4.81 eq. wt. 309.2	C 61.63 H 7.06 N 4.49 eq. wt. 311.5		10.00	
3.	Mono 2, 4-dichloroanilide of <i>n</i> -hexylsuccinic acid	26	97	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ Cl ₂ NO ₂	C 55.85 H 6.18 N 4.32 eq. wt. 339.4	C 55.49 H 6.07 N 4.05 eq. wt. 346.0		100.00	
4.	Mono 3, 4-dichloroanilide of <i>n</i> -hexylsuccinic acid	29	117	" "	C 55.81 H 6.23 N 4.32 eq. wt. 341.1	" "		100.00	
5.	Mono <i>p</i> -methylanilide of <i>n</i> -hexylsuccinic acid	38	120	C ₁₇ H ₂₅ NO ₂	C 70.23 H 8.8 N 5.08 eq. wt. 285.5	C 70.07 H 8.65 N 4.81 eq. wt. 291.0		0.10	
6.	Mono <i>p</i> -methoxyanilide of <i>n</i> -hexylsuccinic acid	65	131	C ₁₇ H ₂₅ NO ₄	C 66.76 H 8.37 N 4.81 eq. wt. 310.1	C 66.45 H 8.14 N 4.56 eq. wt. 307.0		100.00	
7.	Monoanilide of <i>n</i> -decylsuccinic acid	57	106	C ₂₀ H ₃₁ O ₂ N	C 72.21 H 9.63 N 4.58 eq. wt. 328.5	C 72.07 H 9.37 N 4.20 eq. wt. 333.0		400.00	
8.	Mono <i>p</i> -chloroanilide of <i>n</i> -decylsuccinic acid	33	120	C ₂₀ H ₂₉ ClO ₂ N	C 65.52 H 8.34 N 4.01 eq. wt. 360.7	C 65.30 H 8.16 N 3.81 eq. wt. 367.5		1.00	
9.	Mono 2,4-dichloroanilide of <i>n</i> -decylsuccinic acid	18	107	C ₂₀ H ₂₉ Cl ₂ O ₂ N	C 60.01 H 7.43 N 3.61 eq. wt. 394.2	C 59.70 H 7.21 N 3.48 eq. wt. 402.0		10.00	
10.	Mono 2,5-dichloroanilide of <i>n</i> -decylsuccinic acid	52	104	" "	C 60.11 H 7.35 N 3.58 eq. wt. 399.8	C 59.70 H 7.21 N 3.48 eq. wt. 402.0		1.00	
11.	Mono <i>p</i> -methylanilide of <i>n</i> -decylsuccinic acid	43	121	C ₂₁ H ₃₃ O ₂ N	C 72.85 H 9.83 N 4.40 eq. wt. 351.5	C 72.63 H 9.51 N 4.03 eq. wt. 347.0		1.00	
12.	Mono <i>p</i> -methoxyanilide of <i>n</i> -decylsuccinic acid	35	131	C ₂₁ H ₃₃ O ₄ N	C 69.76 H 9.51 N 4.04 eq. wt. 368.0	C 69.4 H 9.09 N 3.85 eq. wt. 365.0		0.10	

(Table 2 Contd.)

13. Monoanilide of <i>n</i> -dodecylsuccinic acid	33	126	$C_{22}H_{36}O_2N$	C 73.51 H 10.12 N 4.13 eq. wt. 363.7	C 73.18 H 9.7 N 3.87 eq. wt. 361.0	400.00
14. Mono <i>p</i> -chloroanilide of <i>n</i> -dodecylsuccinic acid	46	122	$C_{22}H_{34}ClO_2N$	C 67.10 H 8.31 N 3.81 397.5 (eq. wt.)	C 66.76 H 8.60 N 3.54 eq. wt. 395.5	10.00
15. Mono 3, 4-dichloroanilide of <i>n</i> -dodecylsuccinic acid	30	119	$C_{22}H_{32}Cl_2O_2N$	C 61.76 H 7.48 N 3.47 eq. wt. 428	C 61.39 H 7.67 N 3.26 eq. wt. 430	10.00
16. Mono <i>p</i> -methylanilide of <i>n</i> -dodecylsuccinic acid	32	132	$C_{23}H_{37}O_2N$	C 70.96 H 9.65 N 4.08 eq. wt. 388.00	C 73.64 H 9.87 N 3.73 eq. wt. 375.00	100.00
17. Mono <i>p</i> -methoxyanilide of <i>n</i> -dodecylsuccinic acid	31	140	$C_{23}H_{37}O_4N$	C 70.84 H 9.33 N 3.84 eq. wt. 392.5	C 70.58 H 9.46 N 3.58 eq. wt. 391.00	100.00
18. Mono <i>m</i> -chloroanilide of <i>n</i> -dodecylsuccinic acid	15	87.88	$C_{22}H_{34}ClO_2N$	C 67.17 H 8.25 N 3.81 eq. wt. 401.27	C 66.76 H 8.50 N 3.54 eq. wt. 395.50	—
19. Monoanilide of <i>n</i> -hexadecylsuccinic acid	26	144	$C_{26}H_{44}O_2N$	C 75.22 H 10.04 N 3.62 eq. wt. 427.30	C 74.85 H 10.31 N 3.36 eq. wt. 417.00	400.00
20. Mono <i>m</i> -chloroanilide of <i>n</i> -hexadecylsuccinic acid	35	94	$C_{26}H_{42}ClO_2N$	C 69.47 H 9.02 N 3.37 eq. wt. 449.8	C 69.10 H 9.30 N 3.10 eq. wt. 451.5	—
21. Mono <i>o</i> -chloroanilide of <i>n</i> -hexadecylsuccinic acid	22	119	" "	C 69.51 H 9.05 N 3.49 eq. wt. 449.0	" "	400.00
22. Mono <i>p</i> -chloroanilide of <i>n</i> -hexadecylsuccinic acid	35	108	$C_{26}H_{42}ClO_2N$	C 69.52 H 9.14 N 3.46 eq. wt. 449.8	" "	10.00
23. Mono 3, 4-dichloroanilide of <i>n</i> -hexadecylsuccinic acid	48	97	$C_{26}H_{40}Cl_2O_2N$	C 64.60 H 8.25 N 3.21 eq. wt. 488.40	C 64.21 H 8.41 N 2.88 eq. wt. 486.00	100.00
24. Mono <i>p</i> -methylanilide of <i>n</i> -hexadecylsuccinic acid	39	128	$C_{27}H_{46}O_2N$	C 75.47 H 10.09 N 3.62 eq. wt. 427.30	C 75.16 H 10.44 N 3.25 eq. wt. 431.00	10.00
25. Mono <i>p</i> -methoxyanilide of <i>n</i> -hexadecylsuccinic acid	31	126	$C_{27}H_{46}O_4N$	C 72.86 H 9.82 N 3.52 eq. wt. 449.2	C 72.47 H 10.07 N 3.13 eq. wt. 447.00	100.00

the anhydrides(VI) prepared are listed in Table 1. The mono-N-arylamides of the succinic acid are listed in Table 2.

It is obvious that the anhydride(VI) can give rise to two isomeric monoarylamides, (VII) and (VIII). Only one monoarylamide was isolated in each case. Higson and Thorpe⁸ have, without any proof, assigned the structure(VIII, $R=C_6H_{13}$; $Ar=C_6H_5$) to the anilic acid derived from(VI, *d*). On the other hand, Bhide and Ghate⁹ have conclusively proved that the mono-amide derived from phenethyl succinic anhydride(VI, $R=C_6H_5-CH_2CH_2-$) is represented by(VII, $R=C_6H_5-CH_2CH_2$; $Ar=H$). A consideration of the mechanism of formation of the amides from anhydrides would reveal that the formation of(VII) would be favoured slightly over that of(VIII) if the alkyl group is large enough to cause steric hindrance.

The compounds prepared have been tentatively assigned the structure(VII).

Bacteriological screening and results

The *in vitro* tuberculostatic screening of the compounds was carried out in Youman's liquid medium at pH, 7.0. *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* H37RV *var hominis* was used as the test organism.

The medium was incubated for four weeks at 37° prior to inoculation of the drug. The drug was introduced at various dilutions from 400 mcg/ml to 0.1 mcg/ml. The minimum inhibitory concentration is given in Table 2. The standards used for comparison were isonicotinic acid hydrazide(INH) and *p*-aminosalicylic acid (PAS).

It has been found that the ary lamides of *n*-hexyl succinic acid have the highest activity compared to the corresponding amide of the other alkyl succinic acids. Amongst the ary lamides of any particular succinic acid the *p*-chloro-, *p*-methyl- and 2,4-dichloro anilides are the most potent.

Experimental

All m.ps. are uncorrected and were taken in sulphuric acid bath.

Tetradecane-1,1,2-tricarboxylic acid

To an alcoholic solution of sodium ethoxide (1.15 g Na in 15 ml ethanol), diethylmalonate (8 g) was added followed by a gradual addition of ethyl-bromomyristate (17.05 g). The mixture was thereafter refluxed for two hours and then allowed to cool. An aqueous alcoholic solution of sodium hydroxide (4.0 g NaOH in 20 ml of 50% ethanol)

was now added and the mixture refluxed for 6 hours. Removal of alcohol followed by addition of water and acidification with hydrochloric acid liberated the tricarboxylic acid as a pale yellow solid mass. It was obtained as colourless microneedles m.p. 135° (decomp.) from dilute acetic acid, yield 12.5 g.

Found C, 61.56% ; H, 9.67%

$C_{17}H_{20}O_8$ requires C, 61.81 ; H, 9.09%

All other tricarboxylic acids were prepared by the similar method. The other tricarboxylic acids also had m.p. (decomp.) 135°.

n-Dodecylsuccinic acid

The foregoing tricarboxylic acid was heated at 140° till evolution of carbon dioxide ceased completely (30 minutes). The solid mass obtained on cooling, was crystallized from acetic acid as colourless plates m.p. 101°, yield 80%.

n-Dodecylsuccinic anhydride

n-Dodecyl succinic acid (0.033 mole, 9.5 g) was refluxed gently with excess of acetylchloride (8 g) for two hours. Excess of acetylchloride was removed under reduced pressure. The anhydride obtained as a solid mass on cooling, was crystallized from petroleum ether as colourless plates. m.p. 75°, yield 60%.

Found C, 71.98% ; H, 10.81%

$C_{16}H_{28}O_3$ req. C, 71.64% ; H, 10.45%

Monoanilide of n-dodecylsuccinic acid

To a solution of *n*-dodecylsuccinic anhydride (0.01 mole) in dry benzene (10 ml), a solution of freshly distilled aniline (0.01 mole) in benzene (10 ml) was added and refluxed mildly for half and an hour. The reaction mixture was cooled, taken up in sodium bicarbonate solution. The benzene layer was separated and rejected. The

aqueous layer was acidified with hydrochloric acid. The solid obtained was filtered and crystallized from dilute alcohol in fine microneedles, m.p. 126°, yield 33%. The aqueous filtrate was evaporated to dryness on steam bath. The residue was heated with dry ethanol. No pure organic compound could be isolated from this ethanolic solution.

Found C, 73.51% ; H, 10.12% ; N, 4.13%

$C_{22}H_{32}O_3N$ req. C, 73.18% ; H, 9.70% ; N, 3.88%

All other anilides were prepared in the similar way.

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